

GRAsPAD: Generalized framework for optimal grasp key-points active detection

Nikolaos Efstathopoulos¹, Nikolaos Kounalakis², Vasiliki Balaska^{1,3}, John Fasoulas², Dimitrios Papageorgiou^{1,4}

Abstract—In the challenging context of human-robot collaboration, the ability to capture critical human-grasp-related features in a short period is essential for the transfer of skills/experience and the effective imitation learning of human grasping strategies to robotic systems. The paper at hand introduces a novel system for pose optimization of an active (moving) sensor, reducing uncertainty in grasp perception and enabling a more accurate observation of the human grasp pose. The proposed framework, coined as "GRAsPAD" (Generalized fRAMework for optimal graSp key-Points Active Detection), leverages a keypoint detection model to identify grasp-related features in a tomato fruit. The camera pose is iteratively adjusted through the Covariance Matrix Adaptation with Margin - Evolution Strategy (CMAwM-ES) to minimize uncertainty in detected keypoints, enhancing the accuracy of grasp perception and ensuring a clearer, more stable grasp representation. To mitigate sensor noise and variability, a Kalman filter is applied to refine keypoint detections over time. The experimental results demonstrate the significant improvement achieved by the pose optimization of the observer, in terms of grasp perception quality, which is critical for robotic skill learning and effective transfer of human grasping strategies to robotic systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

In contemporary research, the advancement of robotic systems capable of swiftly, accurately, and safely assimilating human processes remains a formidable challenge. Addressing this issue necessitates the design of robust perception systems that can actively adapt their pose to find the optimal observation pose. Within the domain of active perception, the challenge of determining the "Next Best View" (NBV) was first introduced by C. Connolly [1] within the fields of computer vision and robotics. The term "active observer" refers to a sensor capable of adjusting its location and/or orientation in space, with NBV-based methods aiming to identify the optimal pose that maximizes the information about the observed object or scene. Since their first reference hitherto, NBV approaches have been adapted and utilized

in numerous areas—including 3D object reconstruction, autonomous robot navigation, and visual or quality inspection.

Several studies, address object or scene reconstruction, with a large portion of those studies utilizing machine learning techniques—such as 3D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Curriculum and Reinforcement Learning (CRL), Point Cloud Networks, and Random Trees—to identify the next best view [2]–[5]. Additional applications include pose estimation [6], [7] and object recognition or classification [8], [9]. In robotics, NBV has been studied extensively in tasks like localization and navigation [10]–[14], grasping [15], [16], and calibration [17]–[19].

A crucial aspect of perception in robotics, particularly in agriculture and automated harvesting, is the detection and localization of objects in complex environments. In fruit-harvesting robots, vision systems must not only detect ripe and undamaged fruit but also accurately compute their 3D coordinates for robotic manipulation. Various techniques have been explored for fruit recognition, including image segmentation based on color models, feature detection, and machine learning approaches such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) and Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [20]. Additionally, visual servoing has been applied to dynamically adjust the pose of the robotic end-effector in response to occlusions and variations in fruit positioning, leveraging visual feedback for precise interaction [21]. Furthermore, researchers from Wageningen University [22], presented a framework for apple harvesting purposes, which uses gloves with OptiTrack markers to detect and track hand pose.

Although the aforementioned methods, have been used in many fields, their potential use for active optimal state estimation involving a human agent, aiming towards grasp identification, still needs to be investigated. Current approaches are limited around demanding models (RL models or Deep Neural Nets) or they count on external solutions (like gloves) which insert time limitations and consequently prevent them from being usable for human-to-robot skill transfer. In our previous work [23], an active perception framework was proposed for estimating the motion of the human hand, without however focusing on the human grasping.

In this work, in the context of Learning by Demonstration (LbD), we consider the problem of actively perceiving key features of the human grasping of a fruit. In particular, we consider the case in which the human is instructed to keep her/his hand still for the process, involving her/him in the

The research is funded by CARPOS project, carried out within the framework of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan Greece 2.0, funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU (Implementation Body: HFRI). Project Number: 16523.

¹ N. Efstathopoulos, V. Balaska and D. Papageorgiou are with the Dept. of Electrical and Computer Engineering, Hellenic Mediterranean University, 714 10, Heraklion, Crete, Greece. ddk228@edu.hmu.gr

² N. Kounalakis and J. Fasoulas are with the Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, Hellenic Mediterranean University, 714 10, Heraklion, Crete, Greece.

³ V. Balaska is also with the Dept. of Production and Management Engineering, Democritus University of Thrace.

⁴ D. Papageorgiou is also with the Institute of Computer Science, Foundation for Research and Technology–Hellas, Heraklion 700 13, Greece.

active perception loop. As it is important for the human not to shoulder too much physical or cognitive load, the systems aims not only at providing accurate estimates of the features, but also at being fast for facilitating the human involvement and ensuring her/his comfort.

The current work's contributions are the following:

- A method for optimizing of sensor pose (which is considered to be attached to a mechanism) is proposed, allowing rapid adjustment of the sensor viewpoint to improve grasp comprehension.
- To minimize the human partner's physical and mental burden during the process, a clear balance between accuracy and efficiency is sought.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND CONCEPT SOLUTION

One of the key challenges in robotics is still grasping things in unstructured situations, especially for applications like agricultural harvesting. Consider a grasping scenario, such as picking a tomato fruit from a tree. The robot needs to initially identify the most efficient grasping position while accounting for occlusions, changing illumination, and the inherent diversity in the fruit's shape and orientation to do this task effectively.

In the context of Learning by Demonstration (LbD), we consider the case in which the human, who grasps the object, is instructed to keep her/his hand still in order for the system to acquire enough data for detecting the grasp pose. Furthermore, we consider the availability of a moving/actuated sensor, such as an RGB-D camera mounted on the robot's end-effector, to improve perception skills. This sensor can actively change its position and orientation within the 3D space, balancing exploration and exploitation tactics to improve its perspective, in contrast to static perception systems. A conceptual diagram of the considered problem is provided in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: The considered problem. From the initial to the optimal pose.

Let $\{S\}$ be the sensor frame and $\mathbf{c}_p \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_p^T \mathbf{q}_p^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$ be the its pose, where $\mathbf{p}_p \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $\mathbf{q}_p \in \mathbb{S}^3$ are the position and orientation (in a unit quaternion form) of $\{P\}$, with respect to the inertial frame $\{0\}$ respectively, with $\mathbb{S}^n \triangleq \{\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} : \|\mathbf{a}\|=1\} \subset \mathbb{R}^{n+1}$, denoting the set of unit vectors in \mathbb{R}^{n+1} . Furthermore, let ${}^i\mathbf{x}(t) \triangleq {}^i\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$, $i = 1, \dots, N$ be the states of the N observed key points, where ${}^i\mathbf{p}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the position of i -th key point respectively. Due to the fact that the human is instructed to not move her/his hand during the procedure, we consider the state propagation equation for the key-points' dynamics; namely ${}^i\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{0}, \forall i = 1, \dots, N$. As in a real-world case there are slight movements of grasping contact points and also of the detected key-points of fruit due to the lack of human hand's stability and jittering of sensors' detection, respectively, we consider the utilization of Linear Kalman filtering.

Given that the pose of the sensor, i.e. \mathbf{c}_p , is actuated, our aim is to design a framework that is able to efficiently explore and accurately estimate the best pose of the sensor, so that the key points of the grasp are optimally perceived, i.e. with minimal uncertainty.

III. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

We consider the availability of a trajectory planner and a trajectory tracking controller that are able to move the end-effector (with the camera) from its current pose, to a target pose $\mathbf{c}_p^* \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$. One such an option, which is employed in our case, is the utilization of a 5th order polynomial as the trajectory planner and the Closed Loop Inverse Kinematics algorithm (CLIK) for accurately tracking the trajectory generated (for the orientation the logarithmic error is employed for the CLIK algorithm), as we consider a robot accepting joint velocity commands. The motion of the robot is considered to be confined within a subset of $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{S}^3$, e.g. the robot's work-space, parameterized by $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^M$. For instance, if a sphere around a rough estimate of the center of the scene is considered to represent the allowable work-space of the end-effector, the polar coordinates can be utilized and therefore $\xi \triangleq [\phi \ \theta] \in \mathcal{T}$, with $\mathcal{T} \subset \mathbb{R}^M$ the allowable subspace of the parameters defining the work-space of the robot. In other words, $\mathbf{c}_p^* \triangleq \mathbf{c}_p(\xi^*)$, with $\xi^* \in \mathcal{T}$ being the target parameters. Let us highlight that it is crucial that the trajectory generation mechanism should yield a trajectory which satisfies this constraint for all $t > 0$.

For tackling the considered problem, we combine linear Kalman filtering for estimating the state of the perceived key-points, with the Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) algorithm for efficient and fast exploration of the pose/task space of the sensor, as shown in Fig. 2. Preliminaries on both employed algorithms are provided below. Given the above rationale, the problem can be written, in a more mathematically rigorous form, as follows:

$$\xi^* = \arg \max_{\xi \in \mathcal{T}} \mathcal{J}(\xi), \quad (1)$$

where $\mathcal{J}(\xi) \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ a reward function that reflects the information gain, which will be defined later.

Fig. 2: Conceptual diagram of the proposed solution

A. Preliminaries on linear Kalman filtering

The linear Kalman filter, introduced by Rudolf E. Kálmán [24], is a well-known method for state estimation of dynamical systems. The rationale behind Kalman filtering, is that the estimated state emerges from fusing measurements (which contains noise with known statistical properties) and prediction derived from the (theoretical) model of the observed phenomenon/object. In the core of the filter, a dynamic model of the observed system is utilized, which is considered to be known with a specific uncertainty. From a control theory perspective, Kalman filtering is an adaptable state observer that not only estimates the next state, $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, of a discrete-time (with $k \in \mathbb{N}$ representing the discrete time index) linear dynamical system, with n state variables, based on noisy observations, but also calculates the uncertainty for its estimations. Let the following be the considered discrete time model:

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{w}_k, \quad \mathbf{w}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q}_k), \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \mathbf{H}\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k, \quad \mathbf{v}_k \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{\Sigma}_k), \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the model-predicted system state vector in next time step, i.e. $k+1$, $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the estimated system state vector at the current time step, $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the process noise/disturbance with covariance $\mathbf{Q}_k \in S_{++}^n$, with S_{++}^n representing the set of $n \times n$ positive definite matrices. Then, $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the state transition matrix, $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the measured output of the system with $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ being the "so-called" observation matrix, and $\mathbf{v}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ the measurement noise, which is considered to be a random variable with covariance $\mathbf{\Sigma}_k \in S_{++}^m$.

The Kalman filter is structured around two key steps: (A) the prediction step and (B) the update step. The estimate is provided based on the following formulas:

A. Prediction Step:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1} = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1}\mathbf{F}^T + \mathbf{Q}_k. \quad (5)$$

B. Update Step:

$$\mathbf{S}_k \triangleq \mathbf{H}\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}^T + \mathbf{\Sigma}_k \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_k \triangleq \mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}\mathbf{H}_k^T(\mathbf{S}_k)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1} + \mathbf{K}_k(\mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H}_k\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k|k-1}), \quad (8)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k|k} = (\mathbf{I}_n - \mathbf{K}_k\mathbf{H}_k)\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k-1|k-1} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the estimated state of the previous time step, $\mathbf{P}_{k-1|k-1} \in S_{++}^n$ the estimated covariance of previous time step, $\mathbf{S}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is used for the covariance calculation of update stage, and $\mathbf{K}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ is the "so-called" Kalman gain. Lastly, $\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1}, \mathbf{P}_{k|k} \in S_{++}^n$ are the so-called "prior" and "posterior" covariance matrices, respectively, of the uncertainty of the estimate. Given these matrices, the information gain in each step k is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{J}_k \triangleq \log \frac{\det(\mathbf{P}_{k|k-1})}{\det(\mathbf{P}_{k|k})}. \quad (10)$$

The value defined in (10) is utilized in (1) for completing the definition of the optimization problem.

B. Preliminaries on CMA-ES

The Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMA-ES) [25] is a stochastic optimization algorithm for black-box optimization problems. It maintains a multivariate normal distribution that evolves over generations. Given an optimization problem with $\mu \in \mathbb{N}$ tunable parameters, the objective is to seek and find one or more candidate solutions, $\boldsymbol{\xi}^* \in \mathbb{R}^\mu$, that minimize (or maximize) the so-called objective/cost/fitness (or reward) function, $\mathcal{J}(\boldsymbol{\xi}) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. The main idea of CMA-ES is to provide, in each iteration ("generation"), a number of candidate solution for the problem ("offspring"), based on a normal distribution $\mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\xi}, \mathbf{C}^{(g)})$ and a step $\sigma^{(g)} \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, with $\mathbf{C}^{(g)} \in S_{++}^\mu$ and $\sigma^{(g)} \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ being adapted dynamically, where $g \in \{1, \dots, g_{max}\}$ is the generation/iteration index and $g_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$ the maximum number of generations.

The initialization of the CMA-ES algorithm requires the definition of the initial mean value ($\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}} = \boldsymbol{\xi}_0$), initial covariance matrix ($\mathbf{C}^{(1)} = \mathbf{C}_0$), initial step size ($\sigma^{(1)} = \sigma_0$), and the definition of $g_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$, as well as the number of offspring, $\lambda_{max} \in \mathbb{N}$. In the "sampling" stage, the algorithm generates λ_{max} offspring solutions (population size at each generation) by sampling a multivariate normal distribution:

$$\boldsymbol{\xi}_\lambda^{*(g+1)} \sim \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{(g)} + \sigma^{(g)}\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{C}^{(g)}), \quad \lambda = 1, \dots, \lambda_{max} \quad (11)$$

where " \sim " denotes the same distribution on left and right side.

After the generation of the offspring, the algorithm updates the mean value $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{(g)} \rightarrow \tilde{\boldsymbol{\xi}}^{(g+1)}$, the covariance $\mathbf{C}^{(g)} \rightarrow \mathbf{C}^{(g+1)}$ and the step $\sigma^{(g)} \rightarrow \sigma^{(g+1)}$, based on the mean values of the parents, the generated solutions and their previous values. More details about the CMA-ES algorithm can be found in [25].

C. Perception of the human grasp key-points

A vision-based keypoint detection system is integrated using an RGB-D camera. The perception system is composed based on two components: a) YOLOv11 Pose model [26] for the fruit detection and b) the Google's MediaPipe Hands model [27] for the human hand. The YOLOv11 model is trained to detect three structural keypoints on the tomato fruit—the center of the tomato ($\mathbf{p}_{t1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), the "knee" on the peduncle ($\mathbf{p}_{t2} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), and the first junction of the peduncle

with the plant ($\mathbf{p}_{t3} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), as shown in Fig. 3. For the hand detection, the Google’s MediaPipe Hands model [27] is employed, which detects three keypoints of the hand, namely the wrist ($\mathbf{p}_{h1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), the thumb tip ($\mathbf{p}_{h2} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), and the base of the middle finger ($\mathbf{p}_{h3} \in \mathbb{R}^3$), as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Key-points considered.

The YOLOv11 Pose model is able to detect bounding boxes and keypoints in parallel, with keypoints directly regressed as offsets from the bounding box anchor grid. This allows the model to estimate x and y coordinates, associated with a confidence, for each keypoint at multiple scales, using the bounding box as a reference frame. The confidence score indicates the model’s certainty about keypoint visibility, with values close to 1 signifying high confidence and those near 0 suggesting occlusion or uncertainty. The model was trained on an annotated dataset of 480 images, each containing multiple tomato instances, and evaluated on a validation set of 43 images. To ensure accurate object localization relative to the camera frame, the detected 2D keypoints are projected into 3D spatial coordinates using depth information and the camera’s intrinsic parameters.

In general, the RGB-D camera’s keypoint recognition yields depth measurements aligned with the object’s surface rather than its centroid. Therefore, for the detected keypoint $\mathbf{p}_{t1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, which is assumed to be located at the center of the fruit, the provided position by the system is translated inward along the estimated surface normal by half of the object’s size, denoted with $d \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$, which is determined by the camera intrinsics and the bounding box width, in order to provide a more realistic representation:

$$d = \frac{(p_2 - p_1)\zeta}{2f_x}, \quad (12)$$

where $\zeta \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is the average depth of a 3×3 array of pixels around the keypoint, $p_1, p_2 \in \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ are the horizontal pixel coordinates of the bounding box and f_x is the focal length in pixels. Then the surface normal, $\mathbf{n} \in \mathbb{S}^2$ is approximated by selecting four neighboring points around the keypoint and computing two tangent vectors, $\mathbf{t}_1, \mathbf{t}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^3$, as follows:

$$\mathbf{t}_1 = \mathbf{p}_b - \mathbf{p}_a, \quad \mathbf{t}_2 = \mathbf{p}_d - \mathbf{p}_c, \quad \mathbf{n} = \frac{\mathbf{t}_1 \times \mathbf{t}_2}{\|\mathbf{t}_1 \times \mathbf{t}_2\|} \quad (13)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3, i \in \{a, b, c, d\}$, are the points corresponding to pixel locations to the left, right, top, and bottom of the detected keypoint, respectively. The computed normal vector \mathbf{n} is then used to adjust the keypoint inward along the estimated surface direction as follows:

$${}^c\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t1} = \mathbf{p}_1 + d\mathbf{n}, \quad (14)$$

with ${}^c\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t1} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ denoting the position of the center of the fruit, with respect to the camera frame $\{C\}$. This adjustment ensures that the assigned reference frame originates at the center of the tomato rather than at its surface. Based on ${}^c\hat{\mathbf{p}}_{t1}$ and given the forward kinematics of the robot, one can easily yield the position of the key-point w.r.t. the inertial frame. Notice that, to establish a local reference frame for grasping, a coordinate system is constructed based on three detected tomato keypoints, given the three points $\mathbf{p}_{t1}, \mathbf{p}_{t2}, \mathbf{p}_{t3}$, which is however out of the scope of this work.

Hand detection is performed using a pre-trained MediaPipe Hand landmark model. In the first step, a Single-Shot Detector SSD-based palm detection model identifies bounding boxes and their corresponding confidence scores, which are then cropped and passed to the next stage. Then a second deep learning model takes the cropped hand image and directly yields the 21 anatomical hand keypoints. Since MediaPipe only provides relative depth values with respect to the wrist, absolute 3D world coordinates are reconstructed using the camera’s intrinsic parameters and depth projection equations. Leveraging the model’s predicted relative depth values in conjunction with the wrist’s depth provides more reliable results, particularly in cases of occlusion and self-occlusion, compared to directly using depth values at the x, y coordinates.

D. Synthesis of the proposed framework

Focusing on the architecture of the GRASPAD framework, two basic loops are identified: a) the optimization loop and the control loop. The outcome of the framework results from the smooth fusion of these components. Towards abstracting the idea of building the framework, it is important to mention that, two types of parameters are involved in our case. On the one hand, some are associated with the human and robot interaction and the task, such as the total time of the procedure and geometrical aspects of the work-space, such as the considered center of the scene and on the other hand the more technical ones are associated with software or hardware limitations. Some examples of the latter is the time step for the control loop.

For synthesizing the proposed solution, we consider the concatenation of the six key-points, i.e. the ones that are related to both the tomato and the human-hand, as the state of the system, and therefore the full state of the system is selected to be $\mathbf{x} \triangleq [\mathbf{x}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{x}_6^T]^T \triangleq [\mathbf{p}_{h1}^T, \mathbf{p}_{h2}^T, \mathbf{p}_{h3}^T, \mathbf{p}_{t1}^T, \mathbf{p}_{t2}^T, \mathbf{p}_{t3}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{18}$. Hence, in our case, the Kalman filter considers $n = m = 18$.

For defining the measurement uncertainty, we utilize the confidence for each key point of the tomato provided by the YOLOv11 model, as well as the confidence score of the palm

provided by Mediapipe (provided for the whole wrist). More specifically, let $\rho_{t1}, \rho_{t2}, \rho_{t3} \in [0, 1]$ be the confidence of the estimation of the tomato points for $\mathbf{p}_{t1}, \mathbf{p}_{t2}, \mathbf{p}_{t3}$ respectively, and let $\rho_h \in [0, 1]$ the confidence provided for the human hand. Then, the measurement covariance matrix is consider, in our method, to be:

$$\Sigma_k = (\mathbf{R}_{c,k} \otimes \mathbf{I}_6) \underbrace{(\mathbf{I}_6 - \text{diag}(\rho_{t1}, \rho_{t2}, \rho_{t3}, \rho_h, \rho_h, \rho_h))}_{\text{uncertainty of each key-point}},$$

where $\mathbf{R}_{c,k} \in SO(3)$ the rotation matrix describing the orientation of the camera with respect to the world frame at the k -the step, with " \otimes " denoting the Kronecker product. Notice that \mathbf{Q}_k and $\mathbf{P}_{0|0}$ are considered to be tunable parameters. Let us highlight, that when an estimate for a key-point is not provided by the perception algorithm, e.g. possibly due to not being within the field of view or not distinguishable, the corresponding uncertainty is set to a predefined relatively large value (approaching numerical infinity).

The proposed algorithm is depicted in Fig. 4. Notice that the reaching procedure is performed for each child (λ) of each generation (g) in a sequential manner. One important aspect is that the CMA-ES optimization solver is fed, in each optimization iteration, not only when the next target is reached, but also during and along the reaching procedure, in order to be able to exploit possible usable information about the reward. This sampling procedure is performed in a separate reward sampling loop, which lies, in term of frequency, between the fast control loop and the relatively slower high-level optimization loop. The selection of this sampling frequency is considered to be a tunable aspect.

Remark 1. *Although the method is presenting in the context of the grasp of a tomato fruit, it is straight-forward to extend its use to other objects and involving other key-points, by training the perception model accordingly, or even by utilizing a pre-trained model.*

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

For the experimental evaluation, the UR5e robotic manipulator is utilized with an eye-in-hand Realsense D435 RGB-D camera, as depicted in Fig.5. The proposed framework is implemented in Python and it is publicly available¹. For integrating the CMA-ES algorithm within our framework, the "cmaes" Python library is utilized. From this library the CMAwM (CMA-ES with margin) algorithm is employed, in order to ensure that the algorithm will be able to also handle cases in which the reward function exhibits a plateau, i.e. when its gradient of the reward is zero within a relatively large area. The maximum generations for the CMAwM-ES algorithm are set to $g_{max} = 5$, the population size in each generation is set to $\lambda_{max} = 6$, while the initial step is set to $\sigma_0 = 6$ and its initial mean value is set to correspond to the pose of the robot. Furthermore, the model error covariance is arbitrarily selected to be $\mathbf{Q}_k = 10\mathbf{I}_{18}$ and the initial covariance of the estimation is set to $\mathbf{P}_{0|0} = \mathbf{I}_{18}$. The

Fig. 4: Flow chart of the synthesized proposed solution.

trajectory generation and control loop's cycle is selected to be 20ms, while the total time duration for reaching the next candidate solution is set to 5s. The work-space of the robot is constraint on a hemisphere, $c_p(\xi)$, around the estimated center of the scene (which is more than 10cm far from the real center of the scene, for being realistic), with $\xi \triangleq [\phi \theta]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$, with $\theta, \phi \in [\pi/8, \pi/2 - 0.3]$.

For evaluating the framework, two experimental scenarios are considered: a) the active detection of a grasp using a mock up setup with a plastic fruit and a realistic plastic human hand, for extensive evaluation and comparison and b) the active detection of a real human grasping case, involving a real tomato for testing the performance of the method in different light conditions and possible occlusion.

Fig. 5: Experimental setup for the initial evaluation experiments.

¹<https://github.com/efnikos/GRAsPAD>

A. Extensive evaluation of GRASPAD framework in a mockup setup

For extensively evaluating the proposed method, we utilize a mock up setup with a plastic tomato and a human-like plastic hand, as shown in Fig. 5. This specific setup is selected in order to allow the "scanning" of the reward function within the considered workspace of the robot, in order to gain the ground-truth knowledge. To this aim, the workspace of the robot is uniformly sampled at 20×20 points within the ξ -space. For evaluating the performance of the proposed method, three different initial camera poses are considered, and 5 experiments are conducted from each initial pose, i.e. a total of 15 experiments were conducted for this evaluation.

The results of the scanned ground-truth reward, in a heatmap form, as well as the initial ξ_0 and optimal ξ^* found parameters through the proposed scheme are shown in Fig. 6. For presentation purposes, the data gathered from the scanning process are interpolated. Notice that in all 15 experiments the framework consistently identifies an optimal, or near-optimal, observation zone. Let us highlight that the initial view point from the third considered initial pose, i.e. the lowest parameter set within the blue shaded zone in Fig. 6, does not include any key-points from the tomato or the hand, i.e. the hand is initially outside the field of view. However, the proposed framework is able to find the solution, even in this challenging case in which the system is initiated from the center of a plateau. Lastly, let us highlight that the procedure of scanning the whole work-space required approximately 30 minutes, which is deemed to be restrictive given that the human is instructed to hold her/his hand still during the process. On the other hand, the proposed method only required 2.5 minutes (more than 10 times less).

Fig. 6: GRASPAD results over the ground-truth scanned via sampling.

B. Experiment with human and real fruit.

The second experiment involves a real human holding a tomato. Specifically, being aligned with typical real-world cases, two sub-cases are tested, namely a study testing two different light conditions, and a study involving occlusions within the field of view of the camera. The idea behind them was inspired from the fruit picking operations in greenhouses

where light conditions are rarely balanced and leaves or even branches can potentially occlude the view.

Figures 7a and 7b show the GRASPAD resulted view point of the grasp, while Fig. 7c and 7d depicts the resulted parameters ξ^* , as well as the initial ones. The surface in Fig. 7c and 7d are computed by interpolating the explored areas during the proposed optimization procedure. Let us highlight, also, that no key-points from the fruit or hand are visible from the initial view point, in order to challenge the exploration capabilities of the method. Notice how the proposed method remains unaffected by the lighting conditions and the observed key-point are detected with high confidence.

For emulating green-house conditions, a real branch with leaves, from a tomato plant, is placed between the workspace of the robot and the grasping location, to test the performance of the method in cases with occlusions of the view. Figure 8 shows the GRASPAD resulted view point of the grasp, in this case, alongside with the resulted parameter ξ^* . Notice how the reward changed with the existence of the branch, as compared to Fig. 7c and 7d, as the area exhibiting a high reward is significantly reduced in size. Lastly, notice that the proposed method was able to explore the workspace and find the view involving no occlusions, with the key-points being detecting with relatively high confidence.

(a) Balanced light conditions. (b) Imbalanced light exposure conditions.

(c) Results in the balanced light exposure case. (d) Results in the imbalanced light exposure case.

Fig. 7: Optimal resulted view points of the grasp, in two different lighting conditions, as well as the resulted optimal solution, in the parametric space.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, a framework for actively perceiving grasp-related key-points is proposed, considering a robot with an eye-in-hand camera observing a human hand while grasping an object. The proposed framework, named "GRASPAD", leverages AI-based perception algorithms, such as the MediaPipe and YOLO, by combining them with state-of-the-art evolutionary optimization algorithms for finding

(a) Resulted view point, in the case involving occlusion. (b) Resulted parameters, in the case involving occlusion.

Fig. 8: Optimal resulted view points of the grasp, in the case in which occlusions are considered, as well as the resulted optimal solution in the parametric space.

the best view that minimizes the uncertainty. The method is extensively evaluated on a benchmarked mock up setup by conducting multiple experiments from different initial sensor poses, against the case of uniformly sampling the workspace for finding the optimal view-point. Furthermore, the performance of the proposed scheme is also tested on a realistic setup, involving a human and a real fruit, with varying lighting conditions and partial occlusions, emulating greenhouse environmental conditions. The outcomes disclosed that the proposed solution not only fulfills its objective to find the optimal observation pose, but also exhibits fast convergence to the solution, which is a crucial requirement due to the human being in-the-loop. In order to improve the generalizability and robustness of the method, future work will concentrate on expanding the framework's capabilities to dynamic environments with moving objects and human operators, incorporating active perception strategies, and validating the method across a larger range of tasks and robotic platforms.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Connolly, "The determination of next best views," in *Proceedings. 1985 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, vol. 2, 1985, pp. 432–435.
- [2] Z. Yan, H. Yang, and H. Zha, "Active neural mapping," in *Intl. Conf. on Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2023.
- [3] X. Chen, Q. Li, T. Wang, T. Xue, and J. Pang, "Gennbv: Generalizable next-best-view policy for active 3d reconstruction," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2402.16174*, 2024.
- [4] H. Dhimi, V. D. Sharma, and P. Tokekar, "Pred-nbv: Prediction-guided next-best-view planning for 3d object reconstruction," in *2023 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2023, pp. 7149–7154.
- [5] A. Bircher, M. Kamel, K. Alexis, H. Oleynikova, and R. Siegwart, "Receding horizon "next-best-view" planner for 3d exploration," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2016, pp. 1462–1468.
- [6] J. Sock, S. H. Kasaei, L. S. Lopes, and T.-K. Kim, "Multi-view 6d object pose estimation and camera motion planning using rgbd images," in *2017 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision Workshops (ICCVW)*, 2017, pp. 2228–2235.
- [7] A. Doumanoglou, R. Kouskouridas, S. Malassiotis, and T.-K. Kim, "Recovering 6d object pose and predicting next-best-view in the crowd," in *2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2016, pp. 3583–3592.
- [8] Z. Wu, S. Song, A. Khosla, F. Yu, L. Zhang, X. Tang, and J. Xiao, "3d shapenets: A deep representation for volumetric shapes," in *2015 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2015, pp. 1912–1920.
- [9] C. Korbach, M. D. Solbach, R. Memmesheimer, D. Paulus, and J. K. Tsotsos, "Next-best-view estimation based on deep reinforcement learning for active object classification," *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2110.06766, 2021.
- [10] M. Lodel, B. Brito, A. Serra-Gómez, L. Ferranti, R. Babuška, and J. Alonso-Mora, "Where to look next: Learning viewpoint recommendations for informative trajectory planning," in *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE Press, 2022, p. 4466–4472. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA46639.2022.9812190>
- [11] S. Tankasala, R. Mart'in-Mart'in, and M. Pryor, "Beyond shortsighted navigation: Merging best view trajectory planning with robot navigation," *ArXiv*, vol. abs/2408.12513, 2024.
- [12] Z. Ma and J. Chen, "Adaptive path planning method for uavs in complex environments," *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, vol. 115, p. 103133, 2022.
- [13] G. Costante, J. A. Delmerico, M. Werlberger, P. Valigi, and D. Scaramuzza, "Exploiting photometric information for planning under uncertainty," in *International Symposium of Robotics Research*, 2015.
- [14] Z. Zhang and D. Scaramuzza, "Beyond point clouds: Fisher information field for active visual localization," *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 5986–5992, 2019.
- [15] Y. Wu, Y. Zhang, D. Zhu, X. Chen, S. Coleman, W. Sun, X. Hu, and Z. Deng, "Object slam-based active mapping and robotic grasping," *2021 International Conference on 3D Vision (3DV)*, pp. 1372–1381, 2020.
- [16] D. Morrison, P. Corke, and J. Leitner, "Multi-view picking: Next-best-view reaching for improved grasping in clutter," *2019 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, pp. 8762–8768, 2018.
- [17] J. Yang, J. Rebello, and S. L. Waslander, "Next-best-view selection for robot eye-in-hand calibration," *2023 20th Conference on Robots and Vision (CRV)*, pp. 161–168, 2023.
- [18] J. Rebello, A. Das, and S. Waslander, "Autonomous active calibration of a dynamic camera cluster using next-best-view," in *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, 2017, pp. 1484–1489.
- [19] X. Zhang, Y. Xi, Z. Huang, L. Zheng, H. Huang, Y. Xiong, and K. Xu, "Active hand-eye calibration via online accuracy-driven next-best-view selection," *Vis. Comput.*, vol. 39, no. 1, p. 381–391, Jan. 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00371-021-02336-7>
- [20] J. Gao, J. Zhang, F. Zhang, and J. Gao, "Lacta: A lightweight and accurate algorithm for cherry tomato detection in unstructured environments," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 238, no. PC, Mar. 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2023.122073>
- [21] J. Pak, J. Kim, Y. Park, and H. I. Son, "Field evaluation of path-planning algorithms for autonomous mobile robot in smart farms," *IEEE access*, vol. 10, pp. 60 253–60 266, 2022.
- [22] R. van de Ven, A. Leylavi Shoushtari, A. Nieuwenhuizen, G. Kootstra, and E. J. van Henten, "Using learning from demonstration (lfd) to perform the complete apple harvesting task," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 224, p. 109195, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168169924005866>
- [23] D. Papageorgiou, N. Kounalakis, N. Efstathopoulos, J. Fasoulas, and M. Sfakiotakis, "Activo: An active perception framework for skill transfer through iterative visual observations," in *2024 32nd Mediterranean Conference on Control and Automation (MED)*, 2024, pp. 94–100.
- [24] R. E. Kalman, "A New Approach to Linear Filtering and Prediction Problems," *Journal of Basic Engineering*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 35–45, 03 1960. [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.3662552>
- [25] N. Hansen, S. Muller, and P. Koumoutsakos, "Reducing the time complexity of the derandomized evolution strategy with covariance matrix adaptation (CMA-ES)," *Evolutionary Computation*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 1–18, 2003.
- [26] W. Liu, P. Li, and J. Zhang, "Yolov11: Enhancing real-time object detection with improved feature representation," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.17725*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2410.17725>
- [27] F. Zhang, V. Bazarevsky, A. Vakunov, A. Tkachenka, C. Chang, M. Grundmann, and D. Tsytarou, "Mediapipe hands: On-device real-time hand tracking," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.10214*, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2006.10214>